

Exploring Effective Data Visualization Strategies in Higher Education

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Data visualization is a graphic representation of data with the intention of easing ease access to information, enhancing data readability, and strengthening information literacy. Over the past decade, data-informed decision-making has become a crucial part of institutional planning in public higher education. Similar to the private sector, higher education is inundated by data, but is oftentimes limited in its capability to review and interpret information in an efficient manner. Literature posits that by making information palatable and accessible, leaders may be able to more effectively foster an infrastructure around data access and utilization. The following study examines the components across literature that relate to developing effective data visualizations and conducts a mix methods study with higher education professionals to identify alignment with historical themes.

Keywords— data visualization, graphic representation, information literacy, graph literacy

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent literature suggests that data visualization is essential to organization success as Littlewood (2018) found that the “best return on investment in skills for our company was in data visualization, based on its high utility and low time to learn.” Sinar, Ray, and Canwell (2018) also suggest that leaders need to strengthen their data skills. Berinato (2016) supports that data visualization is a must-have skill as many organizational decisions are reliant upon data. Similar to private industry, public higher education is shifting towards data-informed decision-making (Bouwma-Gearhart & Jennifer Collins, 2015) and thus there is an emerging need to build data capacity and information literacy in higher education. The following study examines the components across literature that relate to developing effective data visualizations and conducts a mix method study with higher education professionals to identify alignment with historical themes.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Historical Overview

Graphical displays and statistical visualizations surged in popularity beginning in the early 19th century (Friendly, 2008). Governments eagerly funded statistical documents to use in planning projects and these documents fostered graphical excellence and led to innovations in the field of graphical representation, including line graphs, pie charts, heat maps, and contour plots (Friendly, 2008). By the end of the century, however, graphs were criticized for a variety of reasons. Statistical documents were expensive to produce, and critics argued that graphics were merely “pretty pictures” that obscured truth or at worst, were incapable of stating facts (Friendly, 2008). Graphs were soon considered unnecessary

and misleading and their use dwindled (Friendly, 2008). Many designers were criticized for focusing too much on the visual appearance of their displays rather than the designs’ ability to satisfy the analytical needs of readers (Gribbons & Elser, 1998).

Despite this initial decline, graphs once again became ubiquitous starting in the 1950s (Friendly, 2008). This renewed interest led to innovations in the field and a wider acceptance of graphical methods in general (Friendly 2008), particularly because these visual representations of data made it easier to see patterns and outliers, and this led to more informed decision-making processes (Lurie & Mason, 2007). Organizations from all sectors are collecting data to inform their practices and drive change rather than relying on intuition alone (Brynjolfsson & McElheran, 2016). Researchers argue that “digitization and more specifically big data analytics and data science will deeply impact industries, institutions, and most jobs” (Carillo, 2017). Companies and organizations have recognized the need to hire and retain professionals who can work with big data and analytics (Carillo, 2017). The shift from a business-driven to a data-driven operational model has necessitated changes in American educational curricula in order to meet workforce demands. The US faces a shortage of 140,000 to 190,000 professionals with analytical expertise (Ravindranath, 2014). Data literacy skills are being taught in public schools as early as fifth grade (Ravindranath, 2014). Most public school curricula include explicit instruction in data literacy skills like collecting data, reading graphs, and creating charts in order to better prepare students to fulfill market demands. (Spina, 2017)

With the advent of technology, graphical representations have increased, and consumers have become more accustomed to reading graphical representations rather than prose. Research has shown that consumers are more likely to refer to graphs or other visual representations without referring to axes, footnotes, or other help that may have been available (Swires-Hennessy, 2014). Also, readers often abandon overly complex graphs rather than muddle through their interpretation to make meaning (Evergreen & Metzner, 2013). In other words, as graphs are becoming more widely used, designers must consider how to present data clearly. The controversy over graphical presentations is now ripe with new concerns, but consumers have similar worries as in the past—namely that graphs do not provide a clear picture of the data it is supposed to represent. Because consumers are more willing to spend time digesting and interpreting data visualizations that are better designed (Evergreen & Metzner, 2013), researchers must consider design principles in order to maximize the clarity of their graphical representations.

Principles of Data Presentation

Current design principles stipulate that graphical representations follow certain conventions to ensure clarity and readability. For example, pie charts should always add up to 100%, include a maximum of 6 segments, be sorted by size where appropriate, and start at the 12 o’clock position. They should not use bold primary colors or be presented three dimensionally (Swires-Hennessy, 2014). Because working memory can only hold roughly four bits of information at one time, designers must reduce the number of operating elements

in a given display (Evergreen & Metzner, 2013). Color gradation, extraneous gridlines and decimals, and 3D displays should be avoided (Evergreen & Metzner, 2013). Color palettes should direct audience attention rather than distract readers (Knafllic, 2015).

Rather, designers should strive to simplify visuals to the extent possible in order to aid comprehension (Evergreen & Metzner, 2013). This includes ensuring the visible areas of the bars/segments are in proportion to the data, arranging the data to maximize horizontal text of data labels or axes, and using the shades of the same color when presenting proportions of a variable (Swires-Hennessy, 2014). Additionally, graph background colors should be white or have very subdued colors without any sort of color gradation (Evergreen & Metzner, 2013). When organizing a report, designers should think about valuable real estate and use it to their advantage. In Western contexts, readers tend to focus on the top left corner first, then move across, then down and to the right, in a zigzag pattern (Knafllic, 2015). Designers recommend that a visual should clearly communicate the key message to readers in less than five seconds (Krum, 2014). Designers and researchers must consider all of these aspects while they are creating graphs.

When initially presented with a graph, readers typically focus on the title first, followed by the data region, labels and axes, and legend (Jones et al., 1998). Readers will also spend a significant amount of time viewing the title and legend of the graph over any other component (Jones et al., 1998). Designers and researchers should “make the content and appearance of graph titles eye-catching and appealing to readers” since this section receives the most attention (Jones et al., 1998).

III. CURRENT CONCERNS

ADA Compliance: Users with Disabilities

Society is rapidly becoming more data-driven and the need for a more data-literate populace is increasing. Design principles for data visualization have been refined so that consumers can comprehend documents more easily; however, these principles must be expanded to include accessibility concerns for people with disabilities. When the US government passed the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA), public institutions had to redesign their documents to be more accessible. This includes adding alternate text to graphics, providing raw data tables, using high-contrast color schemes, formatting headings, avoiding flash animation, and avoiding red, green, or yellow color schemes (“How does accessible web design benefit all Web users?” 2018).

Many designers argue that “better accessibility results in better design” (Lajewski, 2017); however, a few modern design practices conflict with ADA compliance regulations. For example, infographics are becoming increasingly popular and many of these designs are highly interactive. Animated infographics “create some motion or change to the design as the reader watches” (Krum, 2014). Many websites now include animated infographic designs built into a web page (Krum, 2014). While these designs might be attractive to a wide audience, they are not advantageous to disabled consumers. Research has found that “blind users tend to avoid dynamic

pages” (Hailpern et al., 2009). Additionally, many interactive websites are clickable, thus requiring consumers to use computer mice in order to navigate the site. Because blind consumers do not use computer mice, they do not have equal access to the information displayed on the website (Hailpern et al., 2009).

Eliminating “chartjunk” is another way to make graphics more accessible. Chartjunk is defined as “graphics embellished with unnecessary decoration that detracts from the data” (Bailey & Pregill, 2014). Graphics are now designed to reduce the amount of work the audience has to do in order to understand the information (Knafllic, 2015), and this makes information more accessible to visually impaired consumers. Nevertheless, research has also shown that chartjunk makes information more memorable. Conflicting evidence further suggests that visual embellishments may benefit the reader and adopting an austere style may not be the best approach to chart design (Bailey & Pregill, 2014). Again, designers must balance two competing concerns—accessibility for disabled consumers and preferences of readers without disabilities.

General Population: Graph Literacy

Data visualization poses issues for non-disabled consumers as well. As previously mentioned, consumers are more likely to read graphical representations rather than prose (Swires-Hennessy, 2014). Despite this change in data consumption habits, research suggests that “students, for a variety of reasons, misread graphs” (Roth & Bowen, 2001). These errors “may be related to mathematics knowledge, reading/language errors, scale errors, or reading-the-axes errors” (Friel et al., 2001). Additionally, research has indicated that certain graphs pose more comprehension issues than others. Histograms in general are “more difficult for students to understand conceptually” (Friel et al., 2001). Box plots are relatively abstract and line graphs “may be more difficult to comprehend than other graphs” (Friel et al., 2001).

Other factors, such as color, also impact how a graph is interpreted. Designers are cautioned against using color as the sole means of representing quantitative information because consumers must constantly reexamine graph legends and thus are more likely to become confused (Shah & Hoeffner, 2002). Additionally, color interpretation varies by audience. For example, green signifies “profits” to financial managers, but “infected” for health care workers (Shah & Hoeffner, 2002). The color yellow might be cheerful in small amounts, but it also signifies cowardice to a Western audience (Evergreen & Metzner, 2013). Color palettes should be carefully considered in order to avoid inadvertently communicating the wrong message to the intended audience.

Finally, consumers read graphs with preconceptions and this may affect how the graph is interpreted. One study claims that viewers “typically expect dependent variables to be plotted as a function of y axis in a line graph, and causal or independent variables to be plotted as a function of the x axis” (Shah & Hoeffner, 2002). When graphs deviate from this pattern, students incorrectly interpret the slope and rate of change in the graph. Research has further found that consumers’ expectations about data affects their interpretation of graphs (Shah & Hoeffner, 2002), a phenomenon referred to as confirmation bias. Although graphs and other visual

representations are much more common than in the past, designers and researchers should not assume that all consumers, particularly students, will comprehend or correctly interpret the data in a graph. For these reasons, it is important to take into consideration design principles and the targeted audience when designing and creating graphical displays of information, be it infographic posters, interactive dashboards, or stagnant reports containing charts and graphs.

IV. METHODS AND FINDINGS

Methods

A set of trainings related to data utilization were hosted across a two-month period, covering topics related to data report repositories, ad-hoc data manipulation tools, and data dashboard utilization. While the training focused on building institutional awareness and increasing the utilization of data tools and resources, the events provided an adequate venue to conduct the study. The 34 participants included tenured faculty, part-time faculty, staff, and managers. After a brief introduction to data visualization, participants were provided access to review an interactive dashboard containing student demographic data, including a range of charts, tables, and filters (Appendix A). The participants were asked to independently assess a visualization (data dashboard) and record their perceptions via a mixed methods questionnaire (Appendix B). The questionnaire was developed based on the principles of data presentation and graph literacy discovered in relevant literature. The components of the instrument included first impressions, readability and ease of comprehension, and visual aspects and functionality of the dashboard.

Findings

The predominant response from the qualitative responses showed that participants indicated that the brighter colors within the visual graphs first grabbed their attention. Additionally, the dashboard filter functions, category labels, and data tables were noted as stand-out features by participants. The quantitative comparison found that 82.8% of the participants suggested that the data dashboard was easy to read and comprehend. Participants were then asked to specify their level of agreement regarding various data dashboard characteristics using a four-point Likert scale.

Table 1 Assessment Components related to Readability and Interpretation

Assessment Components	Mean	Percent
Filters are Easy to Use	3.75	93.8%
Title are Appropriate	3.75	93.8%
Colors are Effective	3.63	90.8%
Charts are Clear	3.58	89.5%
Visually Appealing	3.5	87.5%
Axes are Easy to Understand	3.5	87.5%
Legend is Necessary	2.29	57.3%
There are Distracting Components	1.12	28.0%

The emphasis of the research was to identify the factors within the data visualization related to ease of readability and comprehension. Table 1 presents the results of the participants who indicated that the data dashboard was easy to read and interpret (N=28). The data shows that functionality, titles, colors, and layout of the dashboard were the highest rated components in support of readability and interpretation. These findings strongly relate to graph literacy literature.

V. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

While the research was able to draw associativity to data visualization literature, a limitation of the study was the small sample that participated in the study. Future research should be conducted on a broader scale to validate the findings of the current study and should include questions to exemplify data visualization comprehension.

Additional research should be conducted to identify limitations in data availability in higher education. There is also an opportunity to assess the level that data visualization impacts information literacy and effective decision-making in higher education.

VI. DISCUSSION

The research study examined a range of data visualization literature and identified a set of themes that influenced the development of effective data dashboards. Additionally, a mixed methods study was conducted with higher education professionals to collect data on first impressions, readability, and comprehension of information in data dashboards. The findings of the study concluded that ease of readability and interpretation of data visualization is associated with functionality, titles, color, and layout. These findings align with the themes found in data visualization literature and can be used as a framework to support higher education institutions seeking to advance their data visualization effectiveness.

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APPENDIX A: Student Demographic Dashboard

Academic Year: (Multiple values)
 Semester: Fall
 Branch: (All)
 PT/FT Status: (All)
 Education Goal: (All)

Gender

Age Category

Ethnicity

APPENDIX B: Data Visualization Questionnaire

1. Please select your employee classification.
 - Faculty
 - Staff
 - Manager

2. Please select your Planning Wing affiliation.
 - Administrative Services Wing
 - Instructional Services Wing
 - President's Wing
 - Student Services Wing

3. What was the first component of the dashboard that you noticed?

4. Please specify your experience with reading and interpreting the data dashboard.
 - The dashboard was easy to read and easy to interpret.
 - The dashboard was easy to read and difficult to interpret.
 - The dashboard was difficult to read and difficult to interpret.

5. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
The dashboard was visually appealing overall.				
The colors were effectively utilized to distinguish differences between demographic categories.				
The charts clearly represented the data trends.				
The data filters were easy to use.				
The dashboard title was appropriate for the contents of the dashboard.				
The dashboard contained distracting components.				
The color legend was necessary to understand the data presented.				
The chart axes (x-axis and y-axis) were easy to understand.				